

TABLE I—FORMATION CONSTANTS OF α -HYDROXY ACIDS COMPLEXES WITH In(III)

	$\mu = 0.10 M (NaClO_4)$								
	In(III)-Mandelate			In(III)-Glycollate			In(III)-Lactate		
	30°	40°	50°	30°	40°	50°	30°	40°	50°
Log K_1	3.30	3.28	3.23	3.42	3.32	3.28	3.65	3.61	3.55
Log K_2	3.23	3.19	3.16	2.98	2.95	2.85	3.32	3.30	3.24
Log K_3	2.29	2.26	2.23	2.66	2.62	2.55	2.95	2.90	2.81
Log β_3	8.82	8.73	8.61	9.06	8.89	8.68	9.92	9.81	9.60

In earlier communications^{1,2} from our laboratory stability constants and thermodynamic parameters of glycolates and lactates of In(III) were discussed. In the present communication are reported the step-wise formation constants of In(III) complexes with mandelic acid and compared with that reported earlier for glycolates and lactates of the metal by Chakrawarti *et al.*^{1,2}

All the chemicals used were of either B.D.H. (Analar) or equivalent quality. Standard solutions of the ligand and the metal salt were prepared in doubly distilled water, pH of the solutions were measured using 'Systronics', type 322, pH meter.

Formation constants were calculated by Calvin-Bjerrum's method³ at three temperatures 30°, 40° and 50° in 0.1M ($NaClO_4$) ionic strength. The values of log K_1 , log K_2 and log K_3 were directly read from the formation curve and are recorded in Table I. The corresponding values for glycolic and lactic acids complexes, reported earlier by Chakrawarti *et al.*^{1,2} are also recorded in Table I for comparison.

The pH titrations reveal that in In(III)-mandelic acid system, a precipitate appears at pH ~ 4.55 (cf. ~ 4.60 pH in cases of In(III)-glycolic acid and In(III)-lactic acid systems).

From the formation curves [$\bar{n}$ vs $p[L^-]$] of the metal chelates with mandelic acid, it is observed that in all the cases $\bar{n} \sim 3$ (before precipitation points) thus confirming the formation of three chelates, ML , ML_2 and ML_3 as indicated by pH-metric ratio titrations using Nair and Pande's monovariation method⁴.

The stability order of In(III) complexes with the α -hydroxy acids found is lactates > glycolates > mandelates, which is also the order of the basic strength of the ligands.

References

1. P. B. CHAKRAWARTI and H. N. SHARMA, *Labdev.*, 1973, (in press).
2. P. B. CHAKRAWARTI and H. N. SHARMA, *Vijnan Parishad Anusandhan Patrika* 1974, 17, (1), 13, 53.
3. J. BJERRUM, "Metal Ammine formation in Aqueous Solutions," P. Haase and Sons, Copenhagen, 1941.; KELVIN and WILSON, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 67, 2003—.
4. NAIR and PANDEY, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci.*, 1948, 27A, 286..

Chemical Studies on the Polysaccharides of the seeds of *Phaseolus mungo*

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THE polysaccharide of the seeds of *Phaseolus mungo* (Eng. Black gram) has been the subject of study since it is one of the important pulses cultivated throughout India. Different important products like vitamins¹, amino acids², total soluble sugars³ and mucopolysaccharides⁴ have been isolated from the various parts of the plant.

The seeds were freed from skins, macerated, defatted, deproteinised⁵ and different fractions of polysaccharides were isolated according to the scheme described earlier⁶. The powdered material (30 g) was extracted successively with (1) cold water, (2) boiling water, (3) 0.1N sodium hydroxide solution, and (4) 1.0N sodium hydroxide solution. In the case of water extraction two fractions could be isolated from each of the extracts, the first fraction coming out on addition of minimum quantity of ethanol while the second was precipitated by the addition of excess quantity of ethanol to the supernatant liquid, left after separation of the first fraction. In the case of alkali extraction first fraction was obtained by acidification of the extract to pH 5.0 with 50% aqueous acetic acid solution and the second fraction was precipitated by addition of sufficient quantity of ethanol. Eight fractions were isolated and these were designated as M_1 , M_2 , M_3 , M_4 , M_5 , M_6 , M_7 , and M_8 respectively. Yield: M_1 —0.42 g; M_2 —0.11 g; M_3 —4.10 g; M_4 —0.42 g; M_5 —1.10 g; M_6 —0.81 g; M_7 —0.36 g; M_8 —1.20 g.

The monosaccharide components present in the isolated polysaccharides were identified⁷ by paper chromatography and TLC (solvent systems—ethyl acetate : pyridine : water, 8 : 2 : 1; *n*-butanol : ethanol : water, 5 : 1 : 4; ethyl acetate : pyridine : acetic acid : water, 5 : 5 : 1 : 3; spraying reagents—alkaline solution of silver nitrate and aqueous solution of aniline oxalate (saturated). The ratios of sugar components were estimated by periodate oxidation method⁸ and also colorimetrically. Moisture percentage, ash percentage and optical rotations (0.5% in 0.5N NaOH) were measured. All evaporations

NOTES

TABLE 1—PROPERTIES AND COMPOSITION OF THE CRUDE POLYSACCHARIDES

Polysaccharide fractions	Ash %	Moisture %	Specific rotation	Ratios of sugar components					
				ga	glu	ar	mann	rham	xy
M ₁	nil	6.4	+ 13°	0.7	0.1	1.0	0.1	—	0.1
M ₂	nil	8.2	+ 15°	0.8	0.1	1.0	0.1	—	0.1
M ₃	0.12	5.5	+112°	0.5	21.1	1.0	—	—	1.0
M ₄	0.20	7.4	+ 27°	0.8	1.0	1.0	—	0.2	trace
M ₅	0.18	7.0	+ 31°	0.6	1.2	1.0	—	0.2	trace
M ₆	0.15	8.1	+105°	0.7	10.2	1.0	—	—	—
M ₇	0.25	6.5	+127°	1.2	10.0	1.0	—	—	—
M ₈	0.20	7.0	+ 97°	0.3	10.8	1.0	—	—	0.3

ga—galactose; glu—glucose; ar—arabinose; mann—mannose; rham—rhamnose; xy—xylose.

TABLE 2. PROPERTIES AND COMPOSITION OF THE POLYSACCHARIDE FRACTIONS BEFORE AND AFTER DIASTASE TREATMENT

Polysaccharide fractions	Ash %	Moisture %	Specific rotation	Electrophoretic spots (borate buffer)	Ratios of sugar components			
					ga	glu	ar	xy
M' ₃	nil	6.0	+110°	two (+)	0.5	20.0	1.0	—
M'' ₃	nil	5.5	+ 53°	one (+)	0.5	9.7	1.0	—
M' ₈	0.15	4.5	+ 89°	two (+)	0.3	11.5	1.0	trace
M'' ₈	0.15	5.0	+ 63°	one (+)	0.3	6.2	1.0	—

were carried out *in vacuo* at 30°–40°. The results are shown in Table 1. Third and eighth fractions (M₃ and M₈) were isolated as major quantity and these were chosen for further analysis. These were further purified by reprecipitation technique. Percentage of ash and moisture and specific rotations of the purified polysaccharides (M'₃ and M'₈) are shown in Table 2. From these results it is observed that by purification the xylose component of M'₃ has been eliminated and it has been converted to trace quantity in M'₈. No other substantial change could be made in the composition of either of the polysaccharides. On electrophoresis two distinct spots showing migration towards anode in borate buffer were noted with both M'₃ and M'₈ but no movement was observed in phosphate buffer. These observations suggest the neutral nature of the polysaccharides and that each is a mixture of atleast two polysaccharides. Both M'₃ and M'₈ tested for starch which was then removed by treatment with diastase. Specific rotations of the starch-free fractions (M''₃ and M''₈), their electrophoretic behaviour in borate buffer and their monosaccharide components are shown in Table 2. Movement towards anode in borate buffer as a single spot demonstrate the homogeneity of both the starch-free fractions. The neutral nature is again shown by the absence of movement in phosphate buffer. There is, however, appreciable decrease in specific rotations.

The proportion of glucose in both the polysaccharides is appreciably reduced. Both the starch-free fractions, M''₃ and M''₈ are composed of glucose, galactose and arabinose and these were isolated in pure and homogeneous form. Studies on other physico-chemical properties are now in progress.

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References

1. *Chem. Abs.*, 1956, 5953.
2. N. RAJAGOPALAN *Current Sci.*, 1964, 33, 454.
3. R. PANT and D. R. P. TULSIANI, *Current Sci.*, 1968, 87, 74.
4. S. B. KAKOL, H. S. R. DESIKACHAR and M. SRINIBASAN, *J. Sci. Ind. Res. (India)*, 1961, 20C, 252.
5. E. L. HIRST, J. K. N. JONES and W. O. WALDER, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, 1227.
6. A. K. CHAKRABORTY and C. V. N. RAO, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1969, 46, 1055.
7. BAKER and HULTON, *Biochem. J.*, 1920, 14, 754.
8. E. L. JACKSON in "Organic Reactions", John Wiley and Sons, N.Y., 1944, vol. 2, p. 341.